

IMPULSE

IMmersive digitisation: uPcycling cULtural heritage towards new reviving StratEgies

Deliverable D5.2:

Setting-up IMPULSE
Community of Practice

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Executive Summary

The Deliverable D5.2 articulates the characteristics of the Call for setting up the IMPULSE Community of Practice. The document introduces the main Objectives of the call and of the Community of Practice itself, defining the scope and target audiences that will take part into the community according to three channels of action (Education: Teaching & Learning, Creation: Artistic Research, Connection: Creative Industries) connected to the development of future-oriented prototypes. Furthermore, the document explains the hybrid setting in which the IMCo activities will take place, through a digital working space and dedicated in-person events. Lastly, the main KPIs to monitor the effectiveness of the IMCo throughout the duration of the project are introduced.

Key words:

Hybrid community, Community of Practice, Digital working space, Education, Connection, Creation.

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Abbreviations and Acronyms

Abbreviation / acronym	Description
EC	European Commission
DX	Deliverable number X
WP	Work Package
IMCo	IMPULSE Community of Practice
KPIs	Key Performance Indicators
MSX / TX.X	Milestone number X / Task number X.X
CH	Cultural Heritage

1 IMPULSE and the Community of Practice

IMPULSE Community of Practice (IMCo) is a community that will be set up during the beginning of the project (starting at M4) as the main interlocutor of the partners to collect feedback on the IMPULSE prototypes throughout all the phases of the development process. The IMCo will also serve as a platform to promote connection and exchange with networks interested in IMPULSE topics across Europe and globally. The relevance of the Community will remain after the duration of the project and it is expected to partly aid the sustainability of IMPULSE.

2 Objectives

IMPULSE Community of Practice specific objectives

The IMPULSE Community of Practice **is a working space of connection, education and creation** aiming at fostering more effective peer-to-peer processes to look for, share, and tap into practical knowledge among experts directly involved in the IMPULSE partnership board, ultimately growing into a broader network around academic researchers, artists and CCI practitioners involved in digital cultural heritage practices.

The IMCo will serve **as a platform** to collect feedback during all the phases of the development process of the IMPULSE prototypes (e.g. requirement analysis, design, evaluation) and to showcase the project's results to relevant target groups.

Furthermore, the IMCo is **an aggregator in the prototyping phase** to involve representatives of the target groups to collect constant feedback on the prototypes developed by IMPULSE.

The IMCo has also to be considered **as a medium for connection and practical knowledge exchange** between participants, providing different engagement possibilities, and as a communication tool useful to disseminate the main project results to a targeted public.

Connection to IMPULSE Objectives

IMPULSE Community of Practice connects to **Objective 5, which is about enabling connections and encounters** among researchers, artists, cultural heritage practitioners,

CCSIs, entrepreneurs, local institutions, companies, and other relevant stakeholders, through a profiled and effective engagement.

As such, IMPULSE Community of Practice (IMCo) promotes hands-on discussion boards about IMPULSE's focus areas. It works as a hybrid working space – supported by a digital setting and complemented by in-presence events – for practitioners from academia and industries to share practices and learn together, providing them with a space that cultivates the trans-disciplinary know-how behind IMPULSE's main practical achievements (i.e. prototypes).

3 Scope and Focus Areas

Communities of practice are systems of collective critical inquiry and reflection focused on building a shared expertise cultivated over time, to be transformed into opportunities of exchange, new spillover projects and initiatives, innovation movements connected to CH and virtual worlds. As such, they grow around common interests and challenges by members.

Building on the need to facilitate peer-to-peer communication in sharing best practices, *dos* and *don'ts* coming from different fields, members applying to the IMPULSE Community of Practice will collaborate on practical aspects regarding the *future-oriented prototypes* (MS1, MS2, MS4), as by project proposal.

The prototypes will be created in the following directions:

- **Education: Teaching & Learning**, aiming at exploring and sharing immersive didactic processes and experiences;
- **Creation: Artistic Research**, aiming at expanding digitized heritage through artistic performance and speculative reframing in virtual worlds;
- **Connection: Creative Industries**, delve into different digital asset integration protocols and affording access to content aggregators.

Each prototype will consist of at least two multi-user virtual environments and will include assets from the archives of digitized cultural heritage content, contributed to the project by many of the partner institutions. The creation of these virtual worlds will involve participatory processes and input from artists, researchers, and students as well as a greater audience composed of stakeholders, representatives and participants from CCSIs

To invite and facilitate interaction on specific topics, the IMCo will be built around the prototypes' focus areas: Education: Teaching & Learning, Creation: Artistic Research, Connection: Creative Industries. This will be reflected, for example, in the setting of the digital workspace, that will be organized in three main *learning channels*, each dedicated to the target group of reference; the three areas might be helpful in labeling content in IMCo-related announcements and activities, notifying interested members only.

4 Target Audience

The target groups addressed by the IMPULSE Community of Practice are representatives of the user groups considered by IMPULSE:

1. Researchers, students, doctoral students and young scientists;
2. Artists and practitioners involved in art schools as well as established artists in relevant areas (VR art, interactive art, sound arts, immersive cinema, etc.);
3. Representatives of the creative and cultural and creative industries (computer games, film and animation);
4. Cultural institutions interested in the digital heritage upcycling processes;
5. Policy Makers connected to the valorization of CH.

The IMPULSE Community of Practice will be set up in two rounds. The first round (end at M7) will start by inviting the whole IMPULSE partnership board and existing networks. The second round will involve a broader public, including practitioners active on IMPULSE topics and interested in sharing and learning practices.

5 Setting, engagement, and activities

Hybrid setting: digital and physical

The IMPULSE Community of Practice will follow a hybrid setting:

Digital setting: the IMCo will be supported by an open and easy-to-use digital working space, allowing synchronous and asynchronous text chat, resource sharing via hyperlinks and uploaded files (documents, photos, videos, diagrams), and the possibility to hold video and voice chat.

As by project proposal, Mastodon would have been the platform of choice to build the digital collaborative space. However, after further research carried out by UNIBO consulting NKUA and JU management team, **Discord** has been identified as the most suitable platform to host the IMCo digital workspace as it presents built-in features that enable collaboration between its users. Mastodon will be kept as a tool useful to disseminate IMPULSE events and results and to promote engagement and participation to the IMCo. Discord includes the following features:

- **a welcome screen**, for new visitors of the server so they know what IMCo is about and where to begin;
- **announcements channels**, to broadcast messages beyond your server. Users can “Follow” your announcement channels and receive published updates directly to their own servers;
- **stage channels**, audio conversations involving a small group of participants with up to 1000 community members listening in. Members can ask to be brought up to the stage and join in the conversation for all to see;
- **Membership / Rules Screening**, allowing the set-up of rules that new members must explicitly agree to before they can interact with other members and the server contents;
- **server insights**, providing information about interactions and engagement in the server.

The IMCo’s dedicated server on Discord will be organized in a general channel, along with specific multiple channels dedicated to the three focus areas (Education: Teaching & Learning, Creation: Artistic Research, Connection: Creative Industries). The server will work as a place to meet, collaborate, and share ideas, offering different engagement possibilities, e.g. news only, prototypes feedback, connection, and exchange).

The digital working space will be set up, administrated, and moderated by IMPULSE Partners. The community members when accessing the digital platform will have to adhere to Community Guidelines to ensure that no misconduct happens within the platform. The Community Guidelines will ensure meaningful and respectful interactions between the community members.

Physical setting: IMCo will rely on in-presence events to activate different levels of engagement and stage complementary activities to boost discussion groups on prototypes. The events will be organized in different territories and in hybrid mode to make participation more accessible to the international IMCo members. The main IMCo events will be the IMPULSE Hackathon (Athens) and 3 pre-hackathon IMCo workshops focused on each IMPULSE target group: IMCo Workshop in Leuven, focused

on Academia; IMCo Workshop in Malta, focused on artists and IMCo Workshop in Saarbrücken, focused on CCIs, and the final Conference in Bologna.

Organizational structure

The access to the digital working space will be defined through a selection process based on the Call for Interest. The Call for Interest starts with a digital pre-registration (active at M4) and will be submitted to IMPULSE Partners, existing partners' networks, relevant European communities connected to IMPULSE topics of interest (e.g. digital cultural heritage, immersive technologies, digitization of CH, data, metadata, and paradata for CH, legal aspects of digitization processes). From M4 to M7 the Core Team will evaluate and select the submission received from the Call for Interest based on the representation of IMPULSE target groups (academic researchers, artists and CCIs), with criteria of fair representation in gender, minorities, geographical coverage ensured through an intersectional approach. A first list of selected participants will be officially published at M7. However, the call will remain open to allow new participants to apply. This will help also to track people's interest as project results evolve. The new members of the IMCo will be included in the digital environment and in the hybrid dedicated initiatives.

Engagement process

IMPULSE will use all the communication channels of the Dissemination and Communication Strategy to promote awareness about this "human infrastructure" of the project, and to create a positive circulation of knowledge among its different targets. The engagement process started at M4 during the Kick-Off Meeting in Krakow with partner's pre-registration [Fig.1].

Fig. 1. IMPULSE Kick-off Meeting in Krakow

Moreover, the pool of stakeholders interested in joining the community of practice will be enlarged thanks to the initiatives promoted by IMPULSE-related projects from the local to the global scale, just as organization and professionals connected to the European Cultural Heritage Cloud can be involved in the project's various initiatives.

The engagement process foresees the registration through the [IMCO Form](#) [Fig. 2]

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We are setting-up IMPULSE Community of Practice!

*Interested in entering the metaverse
and shaping the future of how we engage with cultural heritage?*

IMCo is a **place of knowledge exchange** to experiment and learn together, starting by the project's prototypes.

Set in three channels, it is a **European community** working on **immersive experiences** for **digitised cultural heritage**.

EDUCATION

Explore and reflect on immersive didactic processes and experiences.

CREATION

Expand digitised heritage through artistic performance and speculative narratives.

CONNECTION

Delve into different digital asset integration protocols to co-design aggregating APIs.

For whom?

- FIRST ROUND**
IMPULSE partners and connected networks
- SECOND ROUND**
IMCo will open-up to cultural and creative individuals and organizations

**FIRST ROUND
PRE-REGISTRATION**

Fig. 2. IMPULSE Call for the Community of Practice Poster

The IMCo members will be reached by IMPULSE newsletters to be informed about the various opportunities of networking according to the GANTT of the project.

The IMCo structure will allow participation of the members according to different levels of involvement. This can be reflected in how roles in Discord will be designed; as such, they can work as tags, so that each member can participate in and start activities according to more than one "role", based on their preference.

A preliminary list of roles, may include:

- **Student/apprentice:** joining the IMCo to learn and explore methods, tools, and processes behind practices of CH digitalization. Students will join channels of interest and can initiate focus threads, to start conversations or propose themes to be further explored.
- **Expert/Specialist:** joining the IMCo as a practitioner with experience in the field of reference. Experts will join channels of interest and share their methods, tools, and processes, also organizing sprint training sessions, seminars, and initiating similar activities.
- **Networker:** joining the IMCo to grow one or more networks, virtual classrooms, and promote similar initiatives on digitised CH and its experimentation in education, creation (artistic practice), and connection (data aggregation).

Networkers are interested in connecting IMCo to other communities of practices, projects, and/or programs; also, they are interested in looking for people to create, for example, satellite working groups that would build on and contribute to IMPULSE's prototypes.

- **Server keeper/Moderator:** this role is for the team that will assist members of the IMCo on Discord: Moderators will make sure that activities are carried out smoothly and that conversations will be inclusive, polite, and respectful. Moderators are the keepers of a safe server and community.

Specific channels on Discord will be role-locked (i.e. backstage channels for Admins and/or Moderators), so that management and maintenance of the IMCo is ensured. IMPULSE's project management board (JU), as well as UNIBOs team will be subscribed to the Admin and/or Moderator role by default.

Activities

The IMCo will be designed to reach out to the target groups and relevant communities efficiently, creating a collaborative digital working space for members to stay in touch and be updated during the whole duration of the project.

In a co-creative and collaborative perspective, the IMCo will be involved to participate in and provide with concrete feedback to the development of the technological prototypes for CH digitization and adaptation during the project in three different moments that define the pre-Hackathon phase (M8-M24).

In fact, three workshops will be organized (MS17) in hybrid mode to gather the IMCo around showing the advancement of the prototypes and asking for their feedback.

Each workshop will have a specific focus on each target group (see 5.1). The workshops aim to collect impressions, feedback and to test the technological advancement of the prototypes with the practitioners of the sector. This approach will guide the partners to develop and prototype according to the community's needs.

Other activities that the IMCo will be involved in and/or will organize, can be (but not limited to):

- elaboration, discussion, and dissemination of contents about case studies, success stories, and results-oriented showcasing outputs of the project. Members will be encouraged to share pictures/videos illustrating their experiences and practices;

- elaboration, discussion, and dissemination of content linked to key project activities such as the multi-visualization of data related to the main projects results;
- organizing or participating in events for the calls launching; contests for members;
- arranging training sessions, seminars, and podcasts also in connection with Mentoring program (T5.4.1).

6 Monitoring

6.1 Main KPIs

The main KPIs to monitor the effectiveness of the IMPULSE Community of Practice will be:

N. of collaborative spaces: 1

N. of in-person events organized for IMCo members to test IMPULSE prototypes: 4

N. of organizations expand knowledge and capacities through IMPULSE Community of Practice: 40

N. of practitioners expand knowledge and capacities through IMPULSE Community of Practice: 80

N. of people benefiting from co-creation workshops: 60

N. of the IMPULSE Community of Practice members benefiting from exchanges: 60

The IMCo will also support IMPULSE to have a Societal Impact connected to **NEB, SDGs, Green Deal and related projects** such as the Green Education Media project, having digitization at the core of the concept and working on the improvement of the job quality and the support deriving from CCSIs towards society's well-being. IMPULSE ensures additional impact on gathering a diversity of professionals from across disciplines to generate ideas, identifying inspirational projects, practices or concepts.

N. of IMCo members that take part in the final Hackathon: more than 30

Increase % of people that follow the social channels of the project +20% each year

N. of new proposals under different financing programs that involve IMCO members: 3

The IMCo will also **support the project** in addressing impacts on policy and regulation: IMPULSE will develop several solutions that will support recommendation, policies and regulations in the field of digitization.

N. of IMCo members that take part in the testing phase of IMPULSE policy briefs: 15-20

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